

ADMINISTRATIVE PERSPECTIVES FOR SCHOOL MANAGEMENT IN PRIVATE INSTITUTIONS

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Venâncio Ferreira de Oliveira

PhD in Administration from Fumec University. Master in Administration from Unihorizontes. MBA in Strategic Management and Corporate Finance from Centro Universitário Una and graduated in Administration from Centro Universitário Newton Paiva (2008). He is currently an administrator at the Federal University of Minas Gerais - UFMG. He also worked at the Federal Institute of Education, Science and Technology of Espírito Santo in the Bidding and Purchasing Coordination of IFES Montanha and in the Human Resources Management Department of the Rectory, in Vitória - ES, performing his duties in the Coordination of Selection and Human Resources Development. He has experience in the area of Human Resources Management, with an emphasis on the field of people development and in the area of Bidding, Purchasing and Public Budget. He has worked in Public Administration since 2007, in the energy, public safety and education segments. E-mail: venancio.oliver13@gmail.com.

Sérgio Rodrigues de Souza

Graduated in Business Administration. Post-Ph.D. in Psychology. E-mail: srgrodriguesdesouza@gmail.com.

ABSTRACT

This article addresses the topic of administrative perspectives for school management in private institutions. Its objective is to analyze the implementation of new administrative systems in the educational environment and the requirements necessary for the training of those responsible for schools, in view of current demands and the context of a society that is constantly transforming, making the school institution, genuinely, a company with a pedagogical vision, giving up the old management model so that the creativity and autonomy of those led can flow. It is up to the leader to provide means for good communication, whether interpersonal or bureaucratic, providing greater effectiveness in the execution of tasks by professionals, consequently valuing the institution in the competitive market. In this way, we intend to consider strategic proposals from the authors covered, through bibliographical research to implement this system in everyday school life, highlighting the importance of strategic planning for the management of organizations today. To this end, the cited authors present each of the

elements of the planning cycle, focusing on how they are formulated and implemented, as well as their function for the management of institutions. The strategic diagnosis, the definition of organizational guidelines (mission, vision and objective), the conception and implementation of the strategy were addressed, showing that planning, if well applied, can make management more competitive, acting as a communication instrument, monitoring and mainly learning.

Keywords: Administration. Education. Competitiveness.

INTRODUCTION

The word management comes from the Latin term *gestione*, which conveys the meaning of managing, administration or direction and is used to conceptualize the way in which a company manages its different sectors, guiding its employees towards the completion of a single objective, way to enable better productivity with less time and less costs, providing greater profitability.

Managing a school means that the individual who leads it must be equipped with pedagogical knowledge to understand the educational process, understand the function of the school, articulate training policies with management policy – strategic vision and have a new perspective on the construction of the political-pedagogical project which is a tool that enables democratic management.

The concept of School Management, relatively recent, is extremely important for schools to meet the current demands of social life: to educate citizens and also to offer the possibility of acquiring the necessary skills and abilities that facilitate social inclusion. For the sake of better understanding, school management is usually classified into three areas, which function interconnected, in an integrated or systemic way: Pedagogical Management, Human Resources Management and Administrative Management.

When we talk about school management, we think about administration. Therefore, managing a school means managing the resources available. In a society that is vertically hierarchical, only those who have the power and authority to do so can manage. When we talk about school management, we also think about teachers and students. And here the question refers to the role of the teacher, as a facilitator of learning, and the student, as the subject of learning. But teachers are not only asked to teach. They are also asked to organize, learn, lead, execute, innovate, and plan. There are many functions that characterize the work of teachers today.

Generally speaking, schools tend to incorporate teachings and methods from the business world, while companies are increasingly opening themselves up with greater

enthusiasm to an active partnership in the tasks of initial training and, above all, ongoing training of the working population. However, it is not technologies that solve management problems or create new opportunities, but rather their application in an innovative way, naturally including new forms of organizational innovation.

From this perspective, by focusing attention on school management and the role of school managers, the strategy would aim to reduce expenses and costs while increasing revenue and income. A computerized management system is therefore advocated, integrating budgetary, financial and treasury management, human resources, integrated management of the resource center, etc. Alongside this debureaucratization of processes, the subject as a person is valued, providing levels of decision-making to the different educational actors, promoting the delegation of decision-making and the corresponding accountability to individuals or groups of individuals, such as Teachers', Pedagogical, Executive or Scientific Councils.

However, with the high demand in the market, managers must be prepared for changes, always planning their new challenges. To do this, they must be “armed” for external competition, equipped with technological advances, from the resources used for the organization’s general communication to equipment for the workforce. Thus, adapting to the demands of society in general.

Administrative challenges have moved from simply satisfying customers to finding out what they want, to giving them more than they imagine, winning them over. In this sense, there has been a strong growth in the educational sector of private schools, where teaching has become a source of business investment. However, these schools are highly dependent on profit for their maintenance, facing the challenge of competition from other institutions. Thus, schools that do not have a modern administrative system tend to lag behind in the market, resulting in financial failures.

The school environment must provide essential elements for the manager to determine the direction to be followed by the institution. This direction is explained through the organizational guidelines formed by the mission, vision and objectives established by the institution.

The institution's mission is its reason for being and determines its identity. Although defining it is an essential element for the management of any organization, managers often fail to clearly define their mission because they confuse it with the service offered. When this happens, the institution restricts its mission to the mere production of services, failing to see the need it meets, which can limit its perspective in terms of strategic performance in the market.

It is important for the institution to know how to adapt its strategy to the internal and external conditions identified in the diagnosis, so that it is able to put into practice the ways to achieve the expected objectives. The fact is that the school, like any company, provides a service, education, and also has interested customers, the students. This classifies it as a service provider institution. The school is neither outside of society, with absolute autonomy in the face of the facts that stimulate social changes, much less in a relationship of absolute subordination, which makes it a mere reproducer of what occurs on a broader level in society. The school is part of society and has a dialectical relationship with the whole – there is a reciprocal interference that permeates all the institutions that constitute the social. Furthermore, we can see that the school has a contradictory function – at the same time as it is a factor of maintenance, it transforms culture.

The school simultaneously maintains and transforms, influences and is influenced by society. In this sense, the importance of training those who manage schools is highlighted. Their pedagogical knowledge in order to understand the educational process needs to involve a deep philosophical reflection on education, revealing the ethical and political domain and the understanding of autonomy based on respect for diversity, the richness of cultures and the search for overcoming the marked local and regional inequalities in the division and involvement of all.

This paradigm shift, so necessary in schools, must involve the implementation of new practices focused on interaction, participation, involvement and the search for partnerships to solve problems and expand new perspectives in the educational context.

ORGANIZATIONAL STRUCTURE

When proposing higher quality in the provision of services, the means of production must be analyzed, that is, the workforce, material resources and physical structure of the institution. These means are interconnected, depending on the good functioning of the other for their own good functioning. Once provided with different sectors, people and resources, the organization tends to disperse its objectives, resulting in later failures. It is up to the leader to create conditions so that these objectives are aligned in a common direction.

Creating an organizational chart helps with task delegation, providing greater clarity regarding functions. The organizational chart is the graph that represents the formal structure of the company, that is, the arrangement and hierarchy of its departments.

Chiavenato (2000) expresses Taylor's concepts regarding the systematization of tasks, which should be analyzed according to the time and movements required for their execution: "A task is any and all activities performed by someone in their work within the organization. The task constitutes the smallest possible unit within the division of labor in an organization" (CHIAVENATO, 2000, p. 69).

Clearly, this attitude has marked a great leap forward in industrial environments, because if each worker performed the task in a different way, it would result in losses, with delays in service, and with no foreseeable time and costs. The process of globalization and its consequences on strategic alliances and market expansion have contributed to the study of strategy in recent years, as a basis for rethinking the paradigms and management tools used by organizations.

Within a dynamic and competitive environment, in which companies are inserted, it brought to light decisive changes and innovations in market relations, resulting from a dynamic based on the flow of information, new technologies, the search for added value in the organizational chain and the focus on a consumer who is increasingly demanding.

This description suggests a specific decision-making process for managers in a global context and imposes responsibilities committed to sustainable management performance, that is, a level of efficiency that implements effective, consistent and adaptable actions over time, in a scenario where supply is expanded and concepts of quality, market and technological obsolescence are dynamized.

Private educational institutions are directly affected by this new way of understanding production and service relations. In this sense, they are facing the causes of globalization and their managers must be aware of the threats and changes in their markets and the consequent impact of these changes on the internal and external environment.

In this context, private educational institutions, whether in the primary, secondary or higher education segments, must develop a strong business vision in order to rethink paradigms, mission, skills and competencies, in addition to defining new approaches and establishing priorities for the future, ensuring that they are able to remain in a highly competitive market and fulfill their role in society. The private educational sector exerts a significant influence on society, since education plays a fundamental role in the development and growth of a country's global economy. This sector is expanding and is currently ranked in the national rankings as a significant generator of employment and income.

Therefore, managers need to convert the needs of society into opportunities for profitable business. This is also a definition of innovation, and it needs to be emphasized today, when we are so aware of the needs of society, schools, health services, cities and the environment (Drucker, 2002, p. 36)

However, with the passing of time and new market demand, there was a need to give up what Hunter (2004) establishes as the old paradigm, that is, the old management model, so that the creativity and autonomy of those led can flow.

Therefore, it is necessary to improve the structure of organizational charts, where the leader no longer just makes decisions, but must first be willing to absorb the proposals coming from his subordinates in order to implement new systems. The subordinates, in turn, must go from being simple task workers to taking on the role of “the secret to the business” of an organization, since they are the ones who are in direct contact with the customer and know their needs in practice. Therefore, managers need to invest heavily in the qualification of their professionals, and these professionals tend to develop beyond specific skills, improving themselves broadly within their professional objective to meet the increasingly demanding job market.

For Drucker (2002), the administrator is a dynamic and vital element. Without his leadership, resources will always be resources, they will never be transformed into production without his effective management, because the quality and performance of the administrator will be fundamental to the success of the company; that is, he is the one who determines the survival and quality of the institution.

The administration is undergoing an educational process to build a global and diverse system, aiming at a competitive economy, but one that stands out for its competence, integrity and performance.

TEAM MOTIVATION

According to Mezomo (1994), before analyzing the needs of his/her subordinates, a school leader must ask himself/herself the following questions: Who are the students? What needs do they have? How do they learn best? When do they learn best? How are they encouraged to seek knowledge? What is the teacher-student relationship like? How are students assessed? What is the content taught? How is it taught?

Once these questions have been answered, the school manager can work towards the development of the sectors and their needs. According to Maslow (1979), to see people produce, they must be influenced emotionally to do so, establishing what he calls the Theory of

Motivation, which is developed respectively into: self-realization; self-esteem; belonging and love; safety and protection; food, water and housing.

People may not always have the best role within the company, but the leader's role is to encourage and provide conditions for them to be the best in their role. Attitudes such as: periodic performance reviews, collective meetings to solve problems, rewards and/or praise for efforts, group dynamics and concern for training are essential for professionals to feel important, as there is an investment provided in them, motivating them to contribute with greater professional commitment, because "Men and women want to do a good job. If they are given the right environment, they will do it." (Bill Hewlett - cited in Hunter, 2004, p. 97).

In effective schools, administrators act as instructional leaders, supporting the establishment of priorities, evaluating instructional programs, organizing and participating in staff development programs, and emphasizing the importance of student achievement. They also act as human relations leaders, emphasizing the creation and maintenance of a positive school climate and conflict resolution, which includes fostering consensus on goals and methods, and maintaining effective school discipline. It should be noted that motivation, morale, and satisfaction are not the sole responsibilities of administrators.

Teachers and administrators work together to improve the quality of the school environment by creating the conditions necessary for more effective teaching and learning, and by identifying aspects of the work process that are considered to be detrimental to quality engagement. Leadership practices in highly effective schools include supporting the school with clear goals, providing a vision of what a good school is, and encouraging teachers to help them find the resources they need to do their jobs effectively.

Lück (1998) discusses the dimensions of leadership related to effective schools, which are: pedagogical focus of the principal, emphasis on human relations, creation of positive environments, actions aimed at clear, achievable and relevant goals, classroom discipline guaranteed by teachers, in-service training focused on pedagogical issues and continuous monitoring of school activities. Schools where there is interaction between teachers tend to be more effective than those where teachers remain professionally isolated.

The school, the teachers, everything flows and yields, and the community realizes that participatory management takes place in that environment. Well-run schools exhibit a culture of mutual reinforcement of expectations: trust, interaction among employees and participation in the construction of pedagogical, curricular and classroom practice objectives.

The main role of the manager is to know how to keep up with changes and try to expand the school organization's capacity for achievement, leading it to reach its full potential and

become an institution that brings professional pride to its members. Within this concept, the manager must make efforts aimed at developing knowledge, skills and attitudes, so that his/her participatory performance gradually becomes more efficient.

The manager assumes responsibility for the effective implementation of the educational policy of the system and the full development of educational objectives, organizing, streamlining and coordinating all efforts in this regard and controlling all resources for this purpose. Due to his central position in the school, the manager, in the performance of his role, exerts a strong influence on all sectors and people in the school. Lück (1990) reports that the manager must have the ability to influence the environment that depends, to a large extent, on the quality and performance of his staff and the quality of the teaching-learning process.

Indicators of meaning mediation can be found in certain types of managerial attitudes in their interactions with the team, such as:

- Does the manager attribute, through his/her feedback and evaluation, sufficient meaning and associate sociocultural values and appropriate appreciation to the success of his/her team?
- Does the manager share with his/her employees his/her feelings and attitudes regarding the various aspects of shared experiences, both inside and outside the school context?
- Does the manager encourage and stimulate his teachers to seek the meaning of their professional activities, questioning the value and usefulness of their own mediation to their students?

Drucker (2002) emphasizes that the manager's motivation must generate desire and expectations that lead his employees to find solutions and perform activities in order to drive efforts in the same direction, seeking results for the team, ensuring that everyone can achieve the same objective.

Likewise, other parameters of mediated learning, such as the mediation of the feeling of competence, the mediation of the attitude of sharing, the mediation of the challenge and the feeling of belonging, should be discussed and analyzed, as they have equally important implications regarding the qualities of the relationship between the manager and his/her employees.

As a leader who aspires to achieve the transcendent objectives of his professional role, the manager of the educational institution should always keep in mind his essential role as a guide, mediator and source of inspiration for his educators.

SCHOOL MANAGEMENT: A COLLECTIVE CONSTRUCTION PROCESS

Describing the fabric of democratic management in schools has been a challenge for researchers in the field of education, with the aim of verifying the legitimacy of a process in which the school community participates not only in the selection of school administrators, but also in the decisions and search for solutions to the challenges encountered in institutional assessments, as well as in the implementation of actions in their daily lives. The focus of educational management and all didactic-pedagogical work is not only the learning or good educational and social performance of all students, but also the construction of plural citizenship, the ability to live with the new and with all the challenges that arise from it. In order to understand democratic management in schools, we need to have a brief overview of the historical evolution of this type of management in the educational context, and understand how it was established in the complexity of the education system.

The serious problems in education will only be solved when everyone participates in order to achieve true democratization, as this increases the opportunities to create an education that serves everyone within the school environment, since democratic management does not occur in a fragmented and isolated manner within the school unit, but rather through dialogue, sharing of ideas, and growing sense and collective actions that guarantee better quality in the educational process.

We live at the beginning of a millennium full of transformations and ruptures that reach and touch, albeit unevenly, almost all human experiences. The historical situation we face today places us before an extraordinary advance that alters the dynamics of society and its organizations, as well as the values that govern their relationship with the individuals who constitute them. The new developmental pattern, the Capitalist State, whose mainspring is the economic field, has provoked a broad political, economic and cultural restructuring in the process of society's development, the repercussions of which are perceptible in the different productive and institutional sectors, both in the private and, mainly, in the public sphere.

In view of this, private and public organizations, in order to ensure their survival, development and strengthening, promote significant structural and functional changes within themselves in order to better meet the new expectations of today's democratic society and the

quality of their performance. In Brazil, the 1990s represented a unique period in terms of reforms in the State and, consequently, in public services, whose objective was to modernize the State and adapt it to the demands of the global economy, which became the main parameter for guiding public policies in general, and around which social and educational issues are articulated, in particular. Since the establishment of the absolute monarchies, educational goods and services have been consolidated by the functioning of a patrimonialist form of administration, which gave educational institutions the character of property of the sovereign, of a public body on the part of the government.

In contrast to this form of administration, with the aim of replacing force and the power exercised by authoritarian patrimonialist regimes, and with industrial capitalism, the paradigm of bureaucratic administration emerged. Because it was “slow, expensive, self-referential, and little or not at all oriented toward meeting the demands of citizens” (Bresser Pereira, 2001, p. 241), it ended up in crisis, which led state reformers to base themselves on managerial tendencies. Criticism of the bureaucratic model of organizational administration motivated the attempt to overcome its inherent procedural rigidity. Citizens complained about state bureaucracy that did not work, about the inflexibility of systems that no one could change, about programs and organizations that overlapped and made coordination impossible, and about public agencies that seemed more interested in promoting their own businesses than in serving citizens.

In view of this, the aim was to overcome the problems currently presented by bureaucratic administrations, which are distant from citizens, from the real needs of the population and are detached from any type of social control, combined with an increase in the level of centralization of decision-making power, using the parameters of managerial administration. For Bresser Pereira (2001), the solution to overcoming bureaucratic legitimacy was found in managerial public administration, which was disseminated as being inspired by the advances made by business administration, characterized by political and administrative decentralization, a posteriori control, the assumption of limited trust, less rigid hierarchy and service to the citizen.

Due to its excessively formalistic and rigid nature, hierarchical and with little commitment to results, the bureaucratic model of state services has become obsolete in the face of society's perspectives. In contrast, it has become necessary to decentralize, so that decisions can be made based on a closer connection between organizations and the problems that should inspire their objectives and purposes.

Managerial Administration means an attempt to respond to the increase in the economic and social functions of the State, technological development, the globalization of capital and the process of consolidation of democracy, which has led society as a whole to demand greater efficiency and quality in public services (Teixeira, 2004, p. 28).

In the educational context, these changes were configured in the prerogatives of decentralization of public education, pointing to new forms of organization and administration of schools and the system. The attempt to municipalize elementary education that has been seen in Brazil, in some states more than in others, since 1997, with the creation of the National Fund for the Development of Elementary Education (FUNDEF), reflects this trend well.

This decentralization converged in educational policies under the premise of incorporating democratic management in public education, since state reformers, when conceiving decentralization as a way of instilling greater rationality in education, actually ended up giving space to the insertion of a new public education management policy embodied in flexibility, participation and quality. “[...] the decentralization of education in its administrative, financial and pedagogical aspects will occur not only as a transfer of responsibilities from central to local bodies, [...] understood by the state as a need to seek to imbue greater rationality in its management. These are propositions that converge towards new models of public education management, based on more flexible, participatory and decentralized forms of administration of resources and responsibilities” (OLIVEIRA, 2002, p. 129).

Responsibility for autonomy is guaranteed by article 15 of the Law of Guidelines and Bases of National Education No. 9394/96 (LDB) to education systems and schools, by establishing that “education systems will ensure, to the public basic education units that integrate them, progressive degrees of pedagogical and administrative autonomy of financial management, observing the general rules of public financial law”.

Through this autonomy, schools have acquired greater possibilities to decide and resolve their daily issues more quickly. These changes have given school management a democratic character of action to overcome authoritarianism and individualism through the participation of all school levels in the choice of actions that prioritize the social quality of education. Conceptions of school management School institutions are complex, ambiguous, and paradoxical organizations that reflect the management model that their administrator, unconsciously or not, develops within them. Libâneo (2004), considering the political and social purposes of education, presents two very different conceptions of management: the scientific-rational and the socio-critical.

In the scientific-rational conception, as previously mentioned, the school is considered an objective and neutral reality, which functions rationally in a bureaucratic and technical manner. Thus, it can be planned, controlled and evaluated in order to generate more results than the expenditure of resources for its operation, achieving the expected objectives. “Schools that operate in this model give strong weight to the organizational structure, the rigorous definition of positions and functions, the hierarchy of functions, the rules and regulations, the centralized management and the planning with little participation of the people” (Libâneo, 2004, p. 120).

In the sociocritical view, the school is conceived as an organization built by the school community (parents, students, teachers and other bodies) in which the decision-making process and management are developed from the collective. Through interaction and participation, projects and actions and the exercise of collaborative practices seek to achieve common goals. In the sociocritical conception, “the school organization is conceived as a system that brings together people, highlighting the intentional nature of its actions, the importance of social interactions within the group and the school's relations with the sociocultural and political context” (Libâneo, 2004, p. 120).

This author also highlights that other studies, in turn, broaden this range of concepts of school organization and management a little further, namely: technical-scientific, self-management, interpretative and democratic-participative. The technical-scientific concept is based on the hierarchy of positions and functions, on administrative rules and procedures, aiming at the rationalization of work and the efficiency of school services.

Self-management is a concept that focuses on collective responsibility with the direct and equal participation of all members of the institution, valuing the group's ability to create and establish its own rules and procedures, rejecting the exercise of authority and hierarchically structured forms of organization and management that are already defined. The interpretative concept has subjective meanings, intentions and interaction between people as essential elements in the process of school organization and management, in addition to rejecting more precise structures of the way of functioning (rules, strategies and procedures).

The democratic-participatory conception is established in the relationship between management and participation of school members in the pursuit of common objectives assumed by all, defending the collective form of decision-making that depends on individual capacities and responsibilities and coordinated and controlled action. Considering that political positions and conceptions of the role of the school in the formation of the individual are reflected in the conception of school management, Libâneo (2004) corroborates the principles of participatory democratic management as a foundation “in favor of the need to combine the emphasis on

human relations and participation in decisions with effective actions to successfully achieve the specific objectives of the school”, valuing planning, organization, management and evaluation as instruments of the decision-making process. Thus, we will see below how the conception of democratic management emerged within public schools and the principles necessary for it to be consolidated as a form of management that guarantees the social quality of the educational process in educational institutions.

EDUCATIONAL MARKETING

Marketing is the area of knowledge that encompasses all activities concerning exchange relationships, aimed at satisfying consumers' needs and desires. Such needs and desires are satisfied through the purchase of products and services. This purchase may be driven by a physiological need (food, shelter, cold) or psychological need (status, safety, entertainment, etc.).

There are two segments in marketing:

- Micromarketing – is the performance of activities that a company seeks to carry out to anticipate the needs of its customers;
- Macromarketing – is a social process that directs an economic flow of goods and services from products to consumers, to meet consumer market demand.

Marketing changes as society changes, as people's needs change over the years and trends change.

By understanding and studying these motivations for consumption, companies seek to produce goods and services that meet the needs of their target audience. It is through marketing that companies will be able to win over and retain their customers. The job of a marketing professional is to understand and modify consumers' attitudes and behaviors in order to make them more favorable to the organization's objectives. This is only possible within certain limits due to the different individual characteristics of consumers. Those responsible for marketing in organizations must seek to see consumers as they really are, and not as they would like them to be.

The main points of marketing are grouped into the marketing compound or “Marketing Mix” and must be studied to position a company in the market and from there to understand and analyze the fundamentals of marketing known as the 4 “P's”. They are:

- A product or service is what a company creates, produces, develops or informs about according to an existing or generated demand;
- A point is any structure that relates to the distribution and logistics channels that enable the delivery or acquisition of the product to the customer.
- Price is the value attributed to a product or service. We must always take into account cost-benefit and competition;
- Promotion is the effort that the company makes to communicate the existence of its products (or services) to the market and promote them, using the media.

KLOTER (1999) identifies the evolution of what he calls *Neanderthal Marketing* to a new *Marketing*. Characteristics of *Neanderthal Marketing* :

- Equate marketing with sales.
- Emphasize customer acquisition, not customer retention.
- Trying to profit on every transaction instead of profiting by managing the lifetime value of a customer.
- Raise prices based on markup (a percentage of the cost or price of a product added to the cost to arrive at the selling price) rather than determining prices based on targets.
- Plan each communication tool separately instead of integrating them.
- Selling the product instead of trying to understand and meet the real needs of customers.

According to the author, this old marketing thinking is giving way to new ways of thinking. Smart companies are improving their knowledge of the customer, the technologies that connect with them, and their understanding of their economic factors. The new marketing concept consists of inviting the customer to participate in the design of the product. New companies are ready to make their products, services, and conditions more flexible, using more targeted communication media, and integrating their marketing activities to convey a more coherent message to customers.

More technology is being used, including videoconferencing, sales automation, software, websites, intranets and extranets. In this new approach, companies are available seven days a week, 24 hours a day, via toll-free numbers, websites or e-mail. The ability to identify

the most profitable customers and establish different levels of service increases. The view of distribution channels has also changed: they are now seen as partners, not adversaries. In short, companies have found ways to provide superior value to their customers.

This gives rise to the importance of institutional communication, carried out in a variety of ways, whether through sponsoring high-impact events among young people, through mass communication highlighting positive aspects of its performance in society, through open relationships with society, generating valuable partnerships and ensuring broad spontaneous dissemination. Ultimately, it is possible to follow paths that allow the institution to be constantly highlighted, especially in the areas in which it operates, enabling recommendations and references that marketing communication cannot provide.

The current financial scenario culminates in a situation where dropout rates and defaults are causing problems for educational institutions, there is high competition and the low income of students seeking courses in public schools is significant. And because it suffers from long periods of stagnation, private education is one of the areas that most demands innovation, boldness and creativity, exactly where many educational institutions fail, by directing marketing towards television campaigns and relegating the students already present.

Educational marketing, the subject of research in this work, does not only consist of attracting and retaining students, but mainly of retaining them, turning the student into a partner, who believes in the Institution, who is proud to study there and, consequently, sells it free of charge to their friends, relatives and acquaintances.

At first, marketing in the educational sector was largely rejected. It was not possible to see the school as a company, nor education as a product. Those who first declared educational marketing were controversial, ignored and criticized. However, the journey has changed history and inserted marketing into the educational reality. This process intensifies the migratory flow of students from one institution to another, sensitized by the appeal of price, discounts, location or quality. Educational marketing emerges not only with a vision or purpose of responding to students' desires, but also of developing an environment of social transformation through actions that contemplate an ethical-philosophical sieve.

Despite being an element that has been worked on and appreciated in most institutions, educational marketing still suffers from some indifference on the part of education professionals.

As well as knowing about the need to use adapted marketing for educational institutions, educational marketing itself is also the hard work of raising awareness, breaking paradigms and breaking down barriers on the part of those who manage, decide and plan for institutions.

The quality of services and customer service are factors for survival and competitiveness in the business market. Schools need to find a differentiator by changing their methods regarding external customer service.

Often, managers and members of the academic staff do not see it as an extremely important instrument within strategic planning; they do not yet see that the instrument is much broader than selling educational services. Therefore, it is necessary to:

Educational marketing is a central activity of modern institutions, growing in their quest to effectively meet some area of human need. To survive and become successful, institutions must know their markets, attract sufficient resources, convert these resources into appropriate programs, services, and ideas, and distribute them effectively to various consumer audiences (KOTLER & FOX, 1994, p. 23).

Most parents want to personally visit the school where their child will study. They want to know what the physical space is like and the pedagogical planning. Some visit several schools before making a decision and signing the contract. It is important to remember that first impressions are lasting impressions, so it is important for professionals to be polite to each other and to the general public. Providing good service to parents is essential for their safety regarding the environment their children will be attending.

A successful school must make an impact and have commercial representation. When people choose educational institutions, they have not yet gotten to know them internally. Their information about them is based on the conceptual image that schools convey in advertising.

However, it is proposed to value the marketing professional in the school environment, as is done in other business sectors.

The investment must be made considering both fronts, starting an institutional campaign before the entrance exam period and then aligning the marketing campaign, ensuring presence and remembrance in the minds of potential prospects (possible clients for a salesperson or a commercial company).

For Drucker (1993), an Educational System that more effectively promotes the insertion of students in this new job market of postmodern society requires structural changes. Theoretical and methodological reorganization will be necessary in accordance with this paradigm, since learning is not only experience in production processes, but also its combination with intellectual and creative activities.

Educational institutions therefore need to understand and absorb the innovation process in order to exercise and stimulate it in the daily lives of students and teachers. The individual's innovative capacity, which is now also considered capital, derives from numerous factors,

among them, fundamentally, knowledge. And this is the raw material “industrialized” in the teaching-learning processes of educational institutions.

In a general and simplistic way, according to Kotler (2000), it can be said that marketing is a social process through which people and groups of people obtain what they need and desire through the creation, offering and exchange of services. Marketing is a two-way street between the market and organizations, in which the latter seek information on the market about their desires and needs, receiving information in return.

Thinking in this way, all activities related to the search for satisfaction of both professionals and society, whether external or internal, have a direct relationship with the professional responsible for marketing. If the main reason for the existence of institutions is to focus on customers, the actions that will have a positive or negative influence on their satisfaction are held by the professionals responsible for the institutions' marketing.

According to Lück (2003), in the management of educational institutions, the involvement of the community and the appreciation of the participation of the people involved are fundamental, in the issues under discussion and in the process of solving problems, and must be recognized as an indispensable condition for the decision-making process to be effective and, likewise, its implementation.

From this perspective, we see that marketing represents much more than promotional tools; it is a philosophy within organizations, a philosophy that has society and the customer as the main reason for the institution's existence.

Internal marketing aimed at school staff

Marketing strategies must be applied on a daily basis, avoiding frustrations in customer service.

According to Estrada (2007), the effectiveness of organizations in serving the external public is the result of marketing actions implemented for the internal public.

To prepare the internal public for external service, motivation alone is not enough; above all, it is necessary to have a harmonious systematization of communication between one sector and another. For example, in a school, the professionals in the secretariat need to be in tune with the teachers to correctly report the students' grades and absences. And this work is only possible with an impeccable organization of the class diary. From a marketing perspective, well-performed services reflect a good appearance of the institution, demonstrating that it is committed to serving with respect for the interests of its customers.

As another component that has resources to help the institution, the internal environment must inspire motivation and creativity for teamwork. This creates noise-free and transparent

internal communication, i.e., internal marketing as a constantly present tool, demonstrating the degree of value placed on the relationship between the institution and the employee.

Currently, there are three areas that work with internal marketing: human resources, quality and marketing. Internal marketing and relationships cannot be discussed without mentioning marketing in the classroom, because when teachers and staff are involved in a proactive approach, they will be good actors in the mission of marketing.

Although the teaching profession is not seen as such, teachers are the ones who are best placed to conduct the process, and through their talent, they will play the role of leader, encouraging students to study efficiently, directing learning far beyond a simple review of material and into a stronger and more intimate bond between the two. By earning the admiration and respect of students, they can become the living image of the institution's quality and competence, ultimately gaining credibility in the market. There are researchers who advocate including teachers in marketing actions in educational institutions, since they are responsible for "teaching", a factor of great importance in attracting and retaining students.

Before implementing any action, managers need to check the teacher's vision and expectations regarding the institution and marketing and whether they understand the application of this component. Lack of understanding cannot be confused with opposition to the work that is being attempted.

Considering faculty as allies rather than adversaries is an important step towards the evolution of marketing processes in educational institutions. Or, in marketing terms: don't forget to add a fifth "P" to the traditional 4 "P's" when developing your strategic marketing plan: professor.

Marketing is not just a simple tool for publicizing/advertising the school. This component encompasses a series of elements that help develop the quality of educational services. Of course, this will only happen if all stakeholders are involved and aware of the entire process, in order to win over and retain students.

Bekin (2004, p. 49) highlights that "the objective of internal marketing is to make the organization's objectives transparent to the employee, in order to harmonize the employee's objective with the company's overall objective".

Mestieri (2004, p. 108) states that internal marketing is "the management of marketing actions aimed at the internal public of companies and organizations, the employees". And he concludes the process as something that "aims to provide better customer service, to serve the customer. [...] Internal marketing transforms marketing into a present value for the entire organization".

Another important element is to clearly define the intended corporate objectives, whether intermediate or definitive, and how much they are in line with the Human Resources profile, since the main objective of internal marketing is to be an effective instrument of change and motivation to achieve these objectives.

Therefore, it can be said that internal marketing is: [...] a strategic activity that involves all people within an organization. It is the way to integrate discourses, unify positions and share information among the various corporate audiences. Training, developing and transforming people into precursors of a process that seeks to create alliances with the client is to make everyone feel part of the institution. (Colombo, 2005, 127).

It is interesting to note that, when a company adequately develops the concept of internal marketing, one of the first reflections observed as an effective improvement is not located within the organization, but rather outside it, in its relationships with the market, customers, suppliers, community, government, etc.

Brum (1998, p. 16) defines internal marketing as “a set of actions used by a company (or a specific management) to sell its own image to employees and their families”. For Bekin (2004) it means

Facilitate and carry out exchanges, building loyalty in the relationship with the internal public, sharing the business and social objectives of the organization, captivating and cultivating to harmonize and strengthen these relationships and thus improving its image and market value (BEKIN, 2004, p. 1).

Endomarketing emerges with the aim of providing quality service, changing attitudes and motivation, as well as achieving organizational goals.

The issue of “perceived quality” by the customer is an increasingly present factor in the consumption decision and, consequently, in the development of products and services by organizations.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

As a proposal to transform the educational environment into a qualified production environment, the primary focus must first be on the executors of this work, that is, the educators and other employees involved. It is assumed that every professional wants to have their work recognized, whether by their superiors or by their work colleagues. Thus, the school manager must be sensitive to the attitudes needed to help the employee achieve their goals, and must be

attentive to requests, participate in collective suggestions, and provide updated tools that are consistent with the tasks planned. In general, one cannot manage without ignoring flexibility, since one is dealing with people, ideas, and diverse resources, thus opening space for transformations in methods in a continuous and globalizing way.

However, the leader needs to guide his subordinates in relation to the proposed objectives, and must follow a certain discipline so that everyone together achieves success.

To become a manager/leader, you must first adopt the new mindset that a leader is a facilitator and not a boss. When a leader understands that his role is to help others perform better, he will dedicate a large portion of his time and energy to teaching.

Another very important point is the interpersonal relationship between all professionals, and the manager should organize events that reinforce the issue of cooperation and personal and professional respect, being a practical example of this.

By following these attitudes, the school administrator develops in his employees confidence and commitment to the school, where they feel free to develop their creativity, as they can count on support, from incremental ideas, to the resources made available to carry out the work with the students, who in turn, will take advantage of all this performance, producing knowledge in a qualified manner, which results in the satisfaction of these clients, giving the institution merit, with regard to preference and trust in choosing the teaching service.

Considering the private educational institution as a sphere in which pedagogical and business actions coexist, it is necessary to understand it as an organization that is influenced by dynamic demands from internal and external customers. The set of these tasks must result in the improvement of overall performance and the ability to map environments, define its mission, formulate objectives, strategies, indicators and policies.

In view of the above, it is worth highlighting that strategic planning is an extremely important management tool in assisting and guiding the Educational Management of Private Educational Institutions. It is worth remembering that the concept of democratic management explained here as an instrument capable of promoting emancipation and awareness of the political role that each individual plays in the community, both in the school environment and in society and which, therefore, constitutes an instrument of social transformation, is an ideal that began to be constructed in Brazil, from the end of the 1980s, with the political opening.

In this context, the educational process was configured as the basis for the construction of a democratic country. The proposal for democratic management of education develops a series of mechanisms that aim to favor the construction of democratic practices and experiences

within the school environment. As these experiences materialize in the school routine, the potential for democratization of society is built to the same extent.

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